

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OMIKUNLE****FIRST NAME: ADEOLA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 7)
2. The Use of Punctuation in Academic Writing (EUCLID 2024, 16)
3. Similarities and Differences Between American and British English (EUCLID 2024, 25)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 34)
5. Writing Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 41)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2024, 44)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58)

PRINCIPLES FOR GOOD ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

Studying the ACA-401D course has been an enlightening and refreshing experience for me. Enlightening because of the new knowledge gained about academic writing and refreshing because I have had the opportunity to learn some of the course content from some prior studies, which I have been enrolled in at different times in my academic and professional training. The course clearly communicated the expectations from the institution of what my response and major papers should look like throughout my studies at EUCLID.

In the subsequent paragraphs below, I will summarize most of what I have learned from the study material.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Academic essays or scholarly writing are nonfictional writings produced as part of academic work (EUCLID 2024, 7). It is recommended that scholarly essays should be planned to ensure a successful outcome; planning usually involves a great percentage of the writing process; it involves researching the topic and organizing your ideas before writing the essay. The essay is usually divided into: Introduction, Body, and Conclusion.

3) THE USE OF PUNCTUATION IN ACADEMIC WRITING

Chapter 2 discussed the available punctuation marks in the English language and their use. The principle of using as few punctuation marks as necessary while retaining the meaning of a sentence (EUCLID 2024, 16) was recommended with examples in the chapter. All punctuation marks (Apostrophe, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolon, comma, dashes, hyphens, ellipses, exclamation marks, quotation, and question marks) were discussed, and applicable examples were highlighted.

4) SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

Although Chapter 3 infers that American English is preferred for this course, details of the similarities and differences between American and British English were given. Both English variants are very similar, especially with educated or scientific English (EUCLID 2024, 25). A major difference is that American English has a more dominant influence on world English, especially since World War II, because of the US political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide compared to that of the UK (EUCLID 2024, 25). Apart from some differences in spelling, pronunciation, punctuation, and terminology of words, some other factors that determine and impact the differences between the US and UK English variants are Yiddish and Ethnic Jewish Influence, politics, and black English.

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism, being a non-ethical and serious academic offense, was taught in detail in Chapter 4. It explains that plagiarism is recognized by the author of the source of information used in academic writing (EUCLID 2024, 34). Examples of plagiarism were given and explained as well, and the method of avoiding plagiarism, which is "Citation," was explained in detail. Different types of citation and their applications, books, internet sites, etc., were also discussed in this chapter.

6) WRITING STYLE GUIDE

Style guides are usually associated with technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting (EUCLID 2024, 41). Consistency in writing style is very important, especially if the technical writing is by multiple authors. Style guides involve the following: Applying preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font usage, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (UK or US, for example), readership considerations, use of abbreviations, accepted terminology, the use of symbols, voice preferences (active or passive), structure, paragraph numbering, and indentation, the use of headings, the use of lists, trademark or branding considerations, correct usage of punctuations, grammar, and vocabulary.

7) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

The Chicago Manual of Style, also known as the Turabian style, is the preferred style of writing by EUCLID. It is important to note that ‘for general matters of spelling, Chicago recommends using *Webster’s Third New International Dictionary* and its chief abridgment, *Merriam-Webster’s Collegiate Dictionary* in its latest edition (EUCLID 2024, 44). This chapter discusses the three major components of the CMS style, which are Chicago Style and Usage, Chicago Page Format, and Chicago End and Footnotes. The rules of the terms under these categories are explained well in the CMS chapter.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Chapter 7 explained in detail the use of Latin abbreviations in writing. Latin abbreviations are usually used in informal writing, but for business, formal, and technical writing, full sentences or expressions are to be written in plain English language so as not to confuse the reader (EUCLID 2024, 58). Some common Latin abbreviations used in non-technical writing are CV, which means curriculum vitae in Latin and English, and “e.g.,” which means *exempli gratia* in Latin and translated as ‘for example’ in English.

9) CONCLUSION

I have studied the ACA-401D course pack, and it has been very enlightening for me as there were lots of laws given on academic writing. I found the chapters on the use of punctuation, application of writing style, and American versus British English very insightful, and I am excited to continue using the principles I learned as I continue my academic advancement. ACA-401D course pack will be a continual reference guide for me till I attain excellent status in my academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.